

RUBEANIC ACID AND ITS DERIVATIVES AS COLORIMETRIC REAGENTS.
 PART I. SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF COBALT,
 NICKEL, PALLADIUM, SILVER AND RUTHENIUM
 WITH RUBEANIC ACID

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Methods for the spectrophotometric determination of cobalt, nickel and palladium in alcoholic pyridine solutions with rubeanic acid are described. Cobalt has been estimated in presence of copper, nickel and silver by employing potassium cyanide and thiourea as masking agents. An extraction procedure for palladium with *isoamyl* alcohol, using disodium salt of ethylenediamine tetra-acetic acid as sequestering agent, is also described. A method of estimating silver in aqueous medium at pH 4.0–4.6 has been developed. The method for determining ruthenium, as reported by Ayres and Young (*Anal. Chem.*, 1950, 22, 1231), has been modified and improved. The color system in all cases more or less obeys Beer's law and gives values of high sensitivity.

Rubeanic acid has been extensively used as a sensitive and selective colorimetric reagent since its introduction by Ray and Rây (this *Journal*, 1926, 3, 118). It reacts with solutions of Cu^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Pd^{II} , Au^{III} , Pt^{II} , Ag^I , Hg^{II} , Cd^{II} , Fe^{II} and Tl^I , forming coloured precipitates. These precipitates, with the exception of those of iron, gold, mercury, lead, cadmium and thallium, are quite stable at the room temperature.

The acidic character of the reagent depends on its tautomerism among the diamido (baso), the amidoimido (semiacid) and the diimido (acid) forms, the latter two containing the acid group, $-SH$. The complex compounds of rubeanic acid with bivalent metals have been accordingly assigned an inner metallic structure:

Wolbling and Steiger (*Mikrochem.*, 1934, 15, 295), on the basis of analytical results, suggested the following formula for its palladium salt:

However, the possibility of a palladium salt of the acid-form, co-ordinated with two molecules of rubeanic acid, has been indicated by Feigl ("Chemistry of Specific, Selective and Sensitive Reactions", Academic Press Inc., Publishers, New York, p. 250, 1949). Bobtelsky and Eisenstadter (*Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1957, 17, 579) also have reported the formation of compounds like Pd_3R_2 , Pd_1R_1 , Pd_2R_3 and Pd_1R_4 (where $\text{R} = 1$ mol. of rubeanic acid), depending on the concentration of the reagent

and p_n of the medium. Spectrophotometric data indicate that Ru^{III} and Ru^{IV} form the same complexes, $[Ru\ SC(NH)CSNH_2]^{2+}$ and $[Ru\ \{SC(NH)CSNH_2\}_2]$ (Yaffe and Voigt, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 3163).

In analogy with certain nickel mercaptides, Jensen (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1944, 252, 227) considers that the nickel salt of rubeanic acid cannot be a monomeric complex, but it must be formulated with a polymeric structure:

In this, the functioning groups of the ligand are arranged in a *trans* configuration around the central metal ion. This assumption has been strengthened by the work of Amon and Kane (U. S. P., 2, 505, 085/1950; cf. also Bailar Jr., "The Chemistry of Co-ordination Compounds", p. 56, Reinhold Publishing Corp., New York, 1956) who found that when a plastic sheet covered with the precipitate of rubeanic acid metal complex was stretched in one direction, the polymer chains were oriented parallel to each other, which alone could account for the polarisation of transmitted light. The bridging ability of rubeanic acid might also be inferred from a consideration of the structure of the diethyl gold derivative of dithiooxamide (Ewens and Gibson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 431).

A polymeric structure with a *cis* configuration of the following type is also not unlikely:

though the crystal structure of rubeanic acid, as revealed by X-ray measurement is given by a *trans*-form (Long, Markey and Wheatley, *Acta Cryst.*, 1954, 7, 140):

But in solution, the rotation of the compound along the C—C axis might be possible, leading to the formation of metal complexes with a *cis* configuration. The *trans*-form, however, seems to be more favourable from symmetry and steric consideration. The possibility of the formation of a simple salt of the type,

is not likely, as the magnetic values of the nickel and cobalt rubeanates differ widely from those of their simple salts (Rây and Bhar, this *Journal*, 1928, 5, 499).

Certain solvents, in which most of the precipitated metal complexes of rubeanic acid and of its derivatives are only sparingly soluble, can, however, extract the latter from their solutions in pyridine. For example, the cobalt, nickel and palladium rubeanates are easily extracted from their pyridine solution by *isobutyl* or *isoamyl* alcohol, in which the precipitated metal complexes are very sparingly soluble. This seems to suggest that the precipitated polymerised complex rubeanates dissolve in pyridine, possibly giving rise to a pyridine complex of the monomer.

Spot tests and capillary separation methods were employed in the detection of copper, cobalt, nickel, etc. by Rây and other workers (Welcher, "Organic Analytical Reagents", Vol. IV, p. 148, V. Nostrand Comp., Inc., New York, 1948). Methods of estimating copper spectrophotometrically, as described by various workers (Welcher, *loc. cit.*; West and Compere, *Anal. Chem.*, 1949, 21, 628; Miller *et al.*, *Metal Abst.*, 1952, 19, 856; Steinle and Lollar, *J. Amer. Leather Chem. Assoc.*, 1954, 49, 285), involve a great difficulty due to extreme insolubility of the copper compound in aqueous solution. Hence, protective colloids, such as gelatine and gum arabic, have been used for peptisation.

The solubility of nickel rubeanate in pyridine (Ray and Rây, *loc. cit.*) suggested the possibility of a colorimetric estimation of the metal. In fact, pyridine is found to be the most suitable solvent for cobalt, nickel and palladium rubeanates. Solutions in acetone or triethanolamine are less stable. Benzene, toluene, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, ethyl or amyl acetate, *isoamyl* or *isobutyl* alcohol, etc. have little solvent action on the metal rubeanates. Copper rubeanate is sparingly soluble in pyridine. Silver rubeanate is sufficiently soluble in water for its colorimetric estimation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Determination of Cobalt

Cobalt was determined in alcoholic pyridine solution with rubeanic acid, by measuring the colour intensity at 400 m μ , at p_{H} 6.5–7.2. The colour remained unchanged for about 2 hours, and the system was found to obey Beer's law. The sensitivity of the reaction is 0.0043 γ Co/cm² (Sandell) and 0.01 γ Co/cm² (practical). Interferences due to small amounts of nickel, copper and silver may be eliminated by the addition of potassium cyanide and thiourea solutions respectively.

The optical density measurements in the visible region were made with a Unicam SP 600 spectrophotometer, using glass cells having 0.5 cm, 1 cm or 2 cm cross-sections. All p_H measurements or adjustments were made with the help of a Cambridge Bench Type p_H -meter, using glass or alkali electrode and a calomel reference electrode.

Standard cobalt solution was prepared by dissolving cobalt chloride (E. Merck, G.R. quality) in distilled water. The cobalt content of this solution was determined as CoSO_4 .

A 0.1% (w/v) solution of rubeanic acid (prepared by the method of Wollner, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1884, 29, 129) in 95% ethyl alcohol was prepared. This solution remains generally stable for several days.

Freshly distilled pyridine was used for all estimations. L.R. (B.D.H.) quality of pyridine was twice distilled in an all-glass apparatus, and the portion distilling at $115-116^\circ$ was collected.

A 1% potassium cyanide (E. Merck, Extra Pure quality) solution in water was prepared. An almost saturated aqueous solution of thiourea (7.8 g. in 100 c.c. at 25°) was used.

Absorption Curves.—The orange-yellow coloured solution of the complex shows maximum absorption in the ultraviolet region. But rubeanic acid also shows a rather high absorption in that region. Measurements were therefore made at $400 m\mu$, where the absorption of the reagent was comparatively small. Fig. 1 shows the absorption curves of blank (I) and of test solution (II). The absorption of the complex solution against reagent blank is almost constant between 380 and $400 m\mu$.

FIG. 1

Co = 0.974 p.p.m. $p_H = 6.8$. Cell = 1 cm.

FIG. 2

Co = 1.96 p.p.m.

Concentration of Pyridine and Alcohol.—Pyridine (2-3 c.c.), added to the metal salt solution previous to the addition of the reagent, was sufficient to keep the complex in alcoholic (over 70%) solution (25 c.c. final volume).

Reagent Concentration.—A 0.1% solution (1 c.c.) of rubeanic acid was sufficient for an amount of cobalt up to 0.1 mg. Addition of an excess of the reagent had no effect on the optical density of the solution.

Effect of p_H was studied with cobalt solutions containing 1.96 γ Co/c.c. and 3 c.c. of pyridine in a final volume of 25 c.c. Optimum $p_H = 6.5-7.2$ (cf. Fig. 2). The optical density of the blank solution was unaffected by p_H changes.

Beer's Law.—Fig. 3-A shows that the system adheres to Beer's law.

Stability of the Colour.—A solution containing 2 γ Co/c.c., pyridine (2 c.c.) and 1 c.c. of rubeanic acid (total volume 25 c.c.) at $p_H 6.8-7.0$ showed the same absorption for 4 hours. With higher concentrations of cobalt (4 γ), opalescence appeared after 2 hours. The colour was found to be stable below 35°.

Sensitivity.—0.0043 γ Co/cm² (Sandell) and 0.01 γ Co/per cm² (practical).

Effect of Diverse Ions.—Since rubeanic acid reacts with a number of metals, interference occurs when they are present even in small amounts. Addition of complexing agents helps to eliminate this interference in certain cases, e.g., potassium cyanide for nickel, and thiourea for copper and silver.

The tolerance limits of foreign ions (p.p.m.) for 2 p.p.m. Co are: acetate 100, tartrate, citrate, oxalate, phosphate and fluoride 50; MoO₄²⁻ and WO₄²⁻ 500; VO₃⁻ 150; Mn²⁺ 300; Ni²⁺ 12 (in presence of KCN), Ag⁺ 20 and Cu²⁺ 8 (in presence of thiourea), and Fe³⁺ 4 (in presence of fluoride). Bi³⁺, Cr³⁺, Fe²⁺, Cd²⁺, Zn²⁺, Pb²⁺, Hg⁺ & Hg²⁺, Sn²⁺, Pt⁴⁺, Pd²⁺ and Au³⁺ interfere even in very small amounts.

Procedure.—To a very weakly acidic or an almost neutral solution of cobalt (free from the interfering ions) pyridine (2-3 c.c.) and the reagent solution (1 c.c.) were added. The volume was made nearly to 20 c.c. with ethyl alcohol (95%), the p_H adjusted to 6.5-7.2 and the solution finally made up to 25 c.c. with alcohol. The optical density was then measured at 400 m μ against a reagent blank.

Estimation of Cobalt in presence of Nickel.—By the addition of potassium cyanide solution, the pink colour of the nickel complex is completely discharged, while the yellow colour due to cobalt is not appreciably affected. The colour system was found to obey Beer's law (cf. Fig. 3-B). The colour was developed as described above, and before making up the volume, 1 c.c. of 1% potassium cyanide solution was added, followed by 5 c.c. of water. Potassium cyanide solution should always be added only after the development of the colour at the desired p_H values and the optical density measured within half an hour, before the appearance of any precipitate.

Estimation of Cobalt in presence of Copper and Silver.—To the cobalt solution containing copper and/or silver, thiourea solution (5 c.c.) was added, successively followed by 3 c.c. of

water, 2 c.c. of pyridine, 1 c.c. of rubeanic acid solution (p_H now adjusted to 6.5-7.2) and 1 c.c. of KCN solution and the volume made up to 25 c.c. with alcohol. The optical

density was measured at 400 $m\mu$ against a suitable blank. The tolerance limit, when both copper and silver are present together with 2 p.p.m. cobalt is 4 p.p.m. of each.

Estimation of Cobalt in presence of Iron.—Ferric iron develops a yellow colour or turbidity with pyridine, although it does not form any strongly coloured complex with rubeanic acid. Addition of sodium fluoride prevents this. 4 P.p.m. of iron (Fe^{3+}) for 2 p.p.m. of Co is tolerated with 1 c.c. of 0.5% solution of sodium fluoride added before the addition of pyridine and the reagent. The volume is made up as usual to 25 c.c. with alcohol and water (5 c.c.). However, the solution becomes opalescent within 10 to 15 minutes. Hence, measurements were immediately taken after the solution was made up. This method is quite suitable for the detection of cobalt even in the presence of a large amount of iron.

Determination of Nickel

The nickel rubeanate in pyridine yields a pink-coloured solution, which permits the determination of the metal when present in traces. The optical density of the solution, measured at 580 $m\mu$ (p_H 9.5-10.5), was found to obey Beer's law for concentrations of nickel above 1 p.p.m., and gave a sensitivity of 0.0117 Ni/cm^2 (Sandell). The method, though highly sensitive, requires, as in the case of many other standard methods, a preliminary separation of nickel from metals like iron, cobalt, and also from copper, except when using thiourea.

Standard nickel solution was prepared by dissolving a known quantity of nickel chloride (E. Merck, G. R. quality) in distilled water, and determining the nickel content of the solution with dimethylglyoxime. Rubeanic acid, pyridine and thiourea solutions were the same as used in the estimation of cobalt.

Absorption Curves—The pink coloured solution has an absorption maximum at 530 $m\mu$, where the reagent solution shows negligible absorption. Fig. 4 shows the absorption curves of the reagent blank and of nickel rubeanate solutions. The optical density is almost constant between 400 and 440 $m\mu$, but is maximum at 530 $m\mu$ where measurements were made.

FIG. 4

Concentration of Pyridine and Alcohol.—The amount of pyridine added, with all other factors remaining constant (Ni 3 p.p.m., 1 c.c. reagent and $p_H \approx 10$), was varied. The stability and the optical density of the colour system were found to increase with pyridine concentration. Solutions containing 5, 10, 15 and 20 c.c. pyridine in a total volume of 25 c.c. were stable for about 1, 1½, 2½ and 3 hours respectively. Hence, the addition of an excess of pyridine (15-20 c.c.) is necessary for the stability of the solution; this, however, raises its p_H value. The final volume was made up with 95% ethyl alcohol, since water caused turbidity.

Reagent Concentration.—A 0.1% alcoholic rubeanic acid solution (1 c.c.) was sufficient to develop the maximum colour intensity with nickel concentration below 0.2 mg. The optical density was not altered by an excess of the reagent.

Effect of p_H .—The colour intensity was stable for about 2-3 hours at p_H 9.5-10.5.

FIG. 5

But a p_H above 9.8 was preferable at which the colour development was almost instantaneous. Below p_H 9.0, the colour tint was more or less yellow to begin with, which gradually changed to violet and became finally pink. Fig. 5 shows the effect of p_H on the optical density of a solution containing 3.47Ni/c.c., 15 c.c. of pyridine and 1 c.c. of rubeanic acid solution in a total volume of 25 c.c. The measurements were made against water as blank, as the reagent solution was kept constant and was unaffected by p_H change.

Beer's Law.—The system was found to obey Beer's law with nickel concentration exceeding 1 p.p.m. (cf. Fig. 3).

Stability of the Colour.—The absorption of a solution (p_H 10.2) containing 3.4 p.p.m. of Ni, 1 c.c. of rubeanic acid solution and 15 c.c. of pyridine showed no change in optical density for about 3 hours, after which opalescence occurred. The colour was also stable at temperatures up to 35°.

Sensitivity.—0.0117Ni/cm² (Sandell) and 0.047Ni/cm² (practical).

Effect of Diverse Ions.—Interference was caused by metals that reacted with pyridine and/or rubeanic acid, giving precipitates or coloured solutions (cf. under cobalt). As in the case of cobalt, vanadate, molybdate, tungstate and manganese did not interfere with the nickel estimation. Fe^{III} in very small amounts (less than 10 p.p.m.) could be tolerated as the iron colour showed very little absorption at 530 m μ . The pink colour of nickel was discharged by cyanide.

Thiourea was used to eliminate the interferences due to copper (12 p.p.m.) and silver (20 p.p.m.). But the volume should be made up with water, and the optical density measured within 15 minutes.

Procedure.—Pyridine (15-20 c.c.) was added to a nearly neutral or faintly acidic nickel salt solution, which was free from the interfering ions. In the presence of small amounts of copper and silver, an aqueous solution (3-5 c.c.) of thiourea was added. The solution was then treated with 1 c.c. of 0.1% alcoholic solution of rubeanic acid and the p_H adjusted to 9.8-10.5. The volume was made up with alcohol

(or water, if thiourea added) to 25 c.c., and the optical density measured within 30 minutes against the reagent blank.

Determination of Palladium

In presence of pyridine, palladium develops an intense orange-yellow colour with rubeanic acid. Palladium has been estimated spectrophotometrically by this means in alcoholic medium at $410\text{ m}\mu$ between p_n 4.2 and 7.0. The colour is very stable and follows Beer's law. It can be extracted with isoamyl alcohol. The interferences caused by many ions like those of copper, cobalt, nickel, iron, cadmium, etc. can thus be eliminated in presence of disodium salt of ethylenediamine tetra acetic acid, used as a sequestering agent.

Standard palladium solution was prepared by dissolving palladous chloride (Johnson Matthey & Co.) in HCl (conc.) and diluting with distilled water. The palladium content of this solution was determined by dimethylglyoxime. Rubeanic acid solution (0.1%), pyridine and 1% aqueous solution of disodium salt of ethylenediamine tetra-acetic acid were used.

Absorption Curves.—Against a reagent blank, the orange-yellow palladium rubeanate solution showed a maximum optical density at $400\text{--}410\text{ m}\mu$, the latter being chosen for all measurements. Fig. 6 shows the variation of optical density with wave-length of the reagent blank and of the palladium complex solution.

FIG. 6

FIG. 7

Concentration of Pyridine and Alcohol.—Pyridine (3.5 c.c.), when added initially, kept the complex in solution without altering its optical density for many hours. Solutions made up with 95% ethyl alcohol remained unchanged for a long time; but with less than 50% alcohol of the total volume, the solutions turned turbid within 1 to 2 hours.

Reagent Concentration.—A 0.1% alcoholic solution (1 c.c.) of rubeanic acid was found to be sufficient for an amount of palladium up to 0.25 mg. in 25 c.c. Higher reagent concentrations had no effect on the colour intensity.

Effect of p_H on the development and stability of colour was studied by measuring the optical density at 410 m μ of solutions, containing 2.47 Pd, 5 c.c. of pyridine and 1 c.c. of the reagent solution in a total volume of 25 c.c., made up with alcohol. Different p_H values of these solutions were adjusted by the addition of a very dilute acid or ammonia solution. The optimum p_H was found to lie between 4.2 and 7.0, where the maximum colour development was instantaneous (Fig. 7). Above p_H 6.9, the stability of the colour decreased somewhat and the solution became opalescent.

Beer's law was found to hold good for palladium up to 10 p.p.m., above which turbidity set in (Fig. 3).

Stability of the Colour.—The optical density remained unaltered for about 3 days and up to a temperature of 40°.

Sensitivity.—0.0137 Pd/cm² (Sandell) and 0.057 Pd/cm² (practical).

Effect of Diverse Ions.—Cu²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Pt⁴⁺, Au³⁺, Mo⁶⁺, V⁵⁺, Ag⁺ etc. interfered. By using versene as the masking agent and then extracting the colour with isoamyl alcohol, many of these interferences could be eliminated.

Procedure.—To an acid solution of palladium pyridine (5 c.c.) and the reagent solution (1 c.c.) were added. The p_H of the solution was then adjusted to 4.2–7.0 and the volume made up to 25 c.c. with ethyl alcohol. The optical density of this solution was measured at 410 m μ against the reagent blank.

Estimation of Palladium by Solvent Extraction.—Palladium, though it forms a complex with ethylenediamine tetra-acetic acid (which is one of the methods of determining the metal spectrophotometrically; cf. MacNevin and Kriege, *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, 26, 1768), reacts with rubeanic acid in its presence in the usual way. But at low p_H values, versene is precipitated in the free state, and in almost neutral solution the palladium rubeanate complex itself is thrown down on making up the volume. These difficulties were overcome by the addition of 3 c.c. of pyridine, adjusting the p_H below 7.0 and by extracting the colour developed with isoamyl alcohol.

At p_H 7.0, when sufficient amount of versene is added, copper, cobalt and nickel do not form any deeply coloured complex with rubeanic acid. The versene complexes of these metals are not extractable by isoamyl alcohol. Versene also prevents the precipitation of Fe^{III}, cadmium, tin and mercury compounds with pyridine, the versenate complexes of these metals being light coloured or colorless. Molybdate, vanadate and tungstate, which interfere in alcoholic pyridine solution, are also rendered ineffective by this means. Ferrous salt solutions in presence of versene develop a yellow colour with pyridine, which is, however, not extractable with isoamyl alcohol. Palladium in presence of a large number of cations can thus be estimated with rubeanic acid with the addition of pyridine and versenate, and by extraction with isoamyl alcohol.

The intensity of the coloured extract remained unaltered even after 24 hours at the room temperature. The system was found to obey Beer's law, and gave a sensitivity of $0.0137\text{Pd}/\text{cm}^2$ (Sandell).

Procedure.—To the palladium solution a 1% aqueous disodium versenate solution (1.5 c.c.) was added, followed by 3 c.c. of pyridine. The p_{H} was adjusted to ~ 5 to 7 and the solution transferred to a 50 c.c. separating funnel. This was then treated with a 0.1% alcoholic solution of the reagent. The total volume of the mixture should be about 15 to 20 c.c. This was shaken with 5 c.c. of *isoamyl* alcohol and allowed to stand for some time for the separation of layers. The *isoamyl* alcohol layer was collected in a 25 c.c. standard flask. The extraction was repeated twice or thrice with 5 c.c. of *isoamyl* alcohol each time, and the extracts collected in the standard flask. The volume was made up to the mark with *isoamyl* alcohol. A blank was prepared similarly by extracting a solution containing only the reagent, pyridine and sodium versenate. The optical density was measured at $410\text{m}\mu$ against the blank, after filtering the extracts through Whatman No. 1 filter paper to remove suspended water particles. Any precipitation that might occur before extraction should be prevented either by decreasing the volume of the aqueous solution, or by adjusting the p_{H} , or by the addition of an excess of pyridine or versenate solution. Table I shows the approximate amounts of cations that may be tolerated for 0.05 mg. Pd in a total volume of 25 c.c.

TABLE I

Effect of diverse ions. Pd rubeanate, solvent extraction
Pd = 0.05 mg.

Metals	Added as	Na versenate added (1% soln.).	Tolerance limit.	Metals	Added as	Na versenate added (1% soln.)	Tolerance limit.
Co ^{II}	Chloride	1 c.c.	30 mg.	Mo ^{VI}	Amn. molybdate	2	30 μg .
Cu ^I	Sulphate	5	3	V ^V	Na vanadate	4	15
Ni ^{II}	Chloride	2	5	W ^{VI}	Na tungstate	4	20
Fe ^{III}	"	5	10	Hg ^{II}	Chloride	5	10
Fe ^{II}	Fe. amm. sulph.	4*	4	Sn ^{II}	"	5**	10
Cr ^{III}	Chloride	4	10	PL ^{II}	Acetate	2	15
Cd ^{II}	"	2	10	Zn ^{II}	Sulphate	2	15

* Excess pyridine (10 c.c.).

**Saturated versenate soln.

The data recorded in the above table also show the different amounts of versene required to mask the effect of ions concerned. Presence of an excess of versene was always necessary to prevent the precipitation of foreign ions as rubeanates, which might remove some palladium by absorption. In presence of ferrous iron, the palladium rubeanate solution was unstable, turning turbid within a short time. Addition of an excess of pyridine was found to give better results. In this case the volume of the aqueous layer before extraction with *isoamyl* alcohol should be limited to 15 c.c.

Pt^{IV}, Ag^I and Au^{III} reacted with rubeanic acid even in the presence of versene, and their complexes were also extractable with isoamyl alcohol. They therefore interfere with the estimation of palladium.

Determination of Silver

Silver in aqueous medium produces a yellowish brown colour when treated with an alcoholic solution of rubeanic acid. The colour is stable for about one hour. For concentrations of silver above 3γ/c.c., the optical density measured at 390 mμ between p_H 4.0 and 4.6 follows Beer's law. The sensitivity is 0.05γ Ag/cm² (practical).

A solution of silver nitrate (G.R., E. Merck) containing a few drops of nitric acid was used. The silver content was determined as AgCl. A 0.1% rubeanic acid solution in 95% ethyl alcohol was used.

Acetate buffer solution was made by mixing 140 c.c. of 0.2N acetic acid (G.R.) with 60 c.c. of 1N sodium acetate solution. The p_H of this solution was approximately 4.2-4.3.

Absorption Curves.—The yellowish brown colour of silver rubeanate in aqueous medium has its absorption maxima in the ultraviolet region. But since rubeanic acid also showed a rather high absorption in this region, measurements were made at 390 mμ (cf. Fig. 8).

FIG. 8

Ag = 4 p.p.m. $p_H = 4.27$. Cell = 1 cm.

FIG. 9

Reagent Concentration.—Maximum colour intensity was obtained with 1 c.c. of 0.1% alcoholic solution of the reagent, when the silver content was less than 16γ Ag/c.c. Excess of the reagent had no effect on the colour intensity.

Effect of p_H .—The optimum p_H range was found to lie between 4.0 and 4.6 (Fig. 7), where the maximum intensity was attained within a few minutes after the addition of the reagent. The solution gradually turned opalescent at or above p_H 4.6.

Beer's Law.—The system was found to obey Beer's law between 3 and 20γ Ag/per c.c. (Fig. 9).

Stability of the Colour.—The optical density of a solution containing 47 Ag/c.c. remained constant for about 1½ hours, beyond which turbidity appeared. The optical density and the stability of the colour remained unchanged up to 35°.

Sensitivity.—0.057 Ag/cm² (practical).

Effect of Diverse Ions.—The determination of silver by rubeanic acid is possible only in the absence of metals which either give precipitate or coloration with rubeanic acid (cf. under cobalt). These metals even when present in very small amounts interfere with the estimation of silver.

Procedure.—The p_H of the sample solution, containing only silver, was adjusted to 4.0-4.6. This can also be achieved by the addition of 10 c.c. of sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer, added after the reagent solution. A 0.1% alcoholic solution of rubeanic acid (1 c.c.) was then added to the above solution and the volume made up to 25 c.c. with distilled water. The optical density was measured at 390 m μ within 30 minutes, against a suitable blank.

Determination of Ruthenium.

The spectrophotometric determination of ruthenium by rubeanic acid has been reported by Ayres and Young (*loc. cit.*). They observed that a high concentration of hydrochloric acid was required to develop the colour and that a large amount of ethyl alcohol was desirable to prevent the precipitation of the complex. It was further noticed by them that at room temperature the colour developed very slowly, while at elevated temperatures the reaction was more rapid.

A critical examination of the procedure was deemed necessary as some difficulties were experienced, when substituted rubeanic acids were used for the determination of ruthenium. This had led to the following modification of Ayres and Young's method.

Ruthenium trichloride (Johnson Matthey & Co) was dissolved in HCl (conc.) and the volume made up in a standard flask. The solution was standardised according to the method of Gilchrist and Wichers (precipitating as the hydroxide and weighing as the metal; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 2565). 0.2% Rubeanic acid in acetic acid was used as the reagent solution.

FIG. 10

Absorption Curves.—The greenish blue colour of ruthenium rubeanate has its absorption maxima in the region 640-670 $m\mu$ (cf. Fig. 10). The colour was developed by adding 1 c.c. of rubeanic acid solution to ruthenium solution (2 p.p.m.), containing 5 c.c. of a mixture (1:1 by vol.) of ethyl alcohol (95%) and 12*N*-HCl and warming on a water-bath for about 30 minutes. The volume was then made up to 25 c.c. with EtOH-HCl (6*N*) mixture (1:1 by vol.).

Reagent Concentration.—The minimum amount of the reagent required by 0.1 mg. Ru to develop the maximum colour intensity was found to be 1 c.c. of 0.2% rubeanic acid solution in acetic acid. Ayres and Young (*loc. cit.*) added 15 c.c. of the same in 100 c.c. final volume. But addition of an excess of the reagent is disadvantageous, as the region of absorption maxima is less sharp, probably due to the change in the tinge of colour (bluish green).

Effect of Acid Concentration.—The amount of acid-alcohol mixture (1:1 by vol. of 12*N*-HCl and 95% EtOH), added before developing the colour, was varied from 1 c.c. to 10 c.c., and the effect on optical density studied. It was found that variation in acid concentration did not affect the colour intensity. The ruthenium solution used for these studies was already acidic with HCl (about 1*N*). Addition of a large excess of acid, as prescribed by Ayres and Young, is therefore, unnecessary.

Beer's Law Curve.—The colour system closely followed Beer's law for ruthenium concentrations up to 4 p.p.m. (cf. Fig. 3). The previous workers noticed that the concentration limit to which Beer's law was valid, lay below 2.2 p.p.m., using 15 c.c. of the reagent solution for 100 c.c. final volume.

Sensitivity.—0.0117 Ru/cm² (Saudell) and 4.047 Ru/cm² (practical).

Effect of Diverse Ions.—Tolerance limits of foreign ions, especially of the platinum metals, have been determined by Ayres and Young (*loc. cit.*). It was observed that osmium interfered seriously, while platinum, palladium, rhodium and iridium were permissible in very small amounts.

Procedure.—To the ruthenium solution which gave a final concentration of not more than 4 p.p.m., 2.5 c.c. of a mixture (1:1 vol.) of 12*N*-HCl and 95% ethyl alcohol and 1 c.c. of rubeanic acid solution (0.2%) were added. The mixture was warmed on a water-bath for about 30 minutes. The volume was then made up to 25 c.c. with 95% EtOH-6*N*-HCl mixture (1:1 by vol.), and the optical density measured at 670 $m\mu$ against a suitable blank.

The use of *N:N'*-disubstituted (like dimethyl, diethyl, dibenzyl, di-*iso*amyl, di- β -hydroxyethyl and diphenyl) rubeanic acids for the determination of the above mentioned metals, besides copper, will form the subject matter of future communications.